

ENERGY MODELLING PLATFORM FOR EUROPE (EMP-E)

Short organisational summary compiled by

Reiner Lemoine Institut, Germany

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ABSTRACT

The first conference of the “Energy Modelling Platform for Europe“ (EMP-E) took place at the European Commission in Brussels, Belgium on 17-18 May 2017.

The EMP-E was organized as a part of the [REEEM Project](#). It is a deliverable assigned to Reiner Lemoine Institute (RLI) in work package 7. The original plan was to add a special track to an existing European conference on environmental informatics. The idea behind, to give an overview on European energy system modelling and pathway analyses to modellers and policy makers, was discussed by the four LCE 21 projects and the Commission, which resulted in the decision that there should be a separate conference for the EMP-E. The headquarters of the European Commission in Brussels was chosen as the venue for the conference. The RLI acted as the main organiser of the conference with support from the Royal Institute of Technology (KTH), Sweden. The Directorate General for Research and Innovation acted as a partner for the organization in Brussels. The thematic discussions were supported by a scientific committee consisting, in addition to the organisers, of important modelling partners of REEEM (i.e., DTU, USTUTT and UCL), representatives of each LCE 21 project as well as from the Directorate Generale for Energy of the European Commission and the Joint Research Centre (JRC).

The EMP-E conference resulted in two days of active knowledge sharing filled with a wide spectrum of expertise and insights provided by independent researchers and policy makers. The speakers gave information and technical input on international energy system modelling projects, as well as on models themselves resulting in very diverse topics for discussions.

The contributions started with expectations and insights concerning energy system modelling at European Commissions level and with presentations about modelling efforts of important H 2020 projects, such as the EU-Calc¹ and the four LCE (low carbon energy) projects². Later, presentations about pathways, sector coupling, case studies, models, and transparency were given by representatives from various international institutions. The conference was concluded by a poster session, a set of interactive panel discussions, and focus groups (workshops dealing with various crucial focus themes).

The conference is accompanied by a publication edited by KTH, gathering contributions from the participants concerning the key subjects of the conference.

¹ http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/206268_en.html

² <http://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/secure-clean-and-efficient-energy>

The discussion about a probable next conference was already started at the first day of the venue and will be continued in depth after the evaluation of the feedback survey. The first EMP-E meeting has set the base for this endeavour and has shown that there already is a common mindset within the community and a great willingness to cooperate.

This summary will be a very short list with the most important steps of the organisation and it will point to the various links with more information about and from the conference.

TIMELINE OF THE FIRST EMP-E CONFERENCE

The following chart shows the most important steps of the organisation of the EMP-E conference.

LINKS

All preliminary and resulting information (incl. contributions) can be found through to the following links:

Information about the EMP-E and links to the posters and speeches (EMP-E “event site”):

<http://www.reeem.org/index.php/event/european-modelling-platform-for-europe-emp-e-2017-in-brussels/>

The domain <http://www.energymodellingplatform.eu> has been secured for the next 5 years by KTH. It currently points at the above EMP-E event on the REEEM site but all information shall be shifted to an independent place in future.

News about the conference shall be found on the REEEM news (and as well on the RLI-Homepage):

<http://www.reeem.org/index.php/2017/06/01/1st-conference-emp-e-energy-modelling-platform-for-europe/>

<http://reiner-lemoine-institut.de/en/1-konferenz-energy-modeling-platform-for-europe/>

There have been some EMP-E tweets that you can follow under #empe17:

<https://twitter.com/hashtag/EMPE17?src=hash>

FOLLOW UP

Journal:

The subjects of the EMP-E shall be reflected in a peer-reviewed special issue in the Elsevier journal of Energy Strategy Reviews (ESR). The call is attached and is still open until midst of July.

Feedback:

Various channels of feedback were possible: oral, notes on flip charts, mails and also a survey have been sent to get valuable feedback. That will be used to discuss the shape of the next meeting. Moreover, the participants were asked to inform about their energy models and modelling platforms in a dedicated stand in the entrance hall of the venue. As such, at the end of the conference, a comprehensive table was created that demonstrates the tools and models used for energy-system analyses in different European institutions.

APPENDIX

In the appendix you find the main organisational documents:

- One representative Invitation
- Handout
 - Agenda
 - List of participants
 - List of posters)
- Call For Papers

Energy Modelling Platform for Europe (EMP-E) Start-up meeting 2017, May 17 – 18, EC headquarters, Brussels

Horizon 2020 project REEEM is pleased to invite you to the First Meeting of an Energy Modelling Platform for Europe (EMP-E) 2017, hosted on May 17th and 18th by the European Commission DG Research & Innovation in Brussels.

The objective of this first EMP-E meeting is to provide a peer-reviewed digest of model and policy insights for European energy scenario projects. It aims to initiate a long-term forum for exchanging research, development and practice of energy system modelling in Europe and, where feasible, promote the sharing of data and resources and improve the efficiency of research in the area. The results of the meeting will be published in a special issue of the journal “Energy Strategy Reviews”, which will be provided as input to high-level events such as COP23¹ in Bonn.

Furthermore, as a first meeting it provides the possibility to discuss future EMP-E meeting structure and format with the aim to propose follow-up meetings. The EMP-E fulfils a recommendation of the Horizon 2020 Advisory Group² for Energy to set up a European forum for energy modelling³.

The agenda includes plenary speeches from the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre and the Directorate-General for Energy as well as from more than 10 large scale EU energy modelling projects, 6 focus groups on crucial modelling subjects and a networking space.

The **networking space** is structured as an open space where all participants, from decision makers to invited projects, can meet and exchange on common questions. We want to make the networking space a central part of the conference, from which you should get an overview about the EU Model-landscape and an insight to ongoing projects.

Therefore you are invited to contribute to the EMP-E with an insight into your models (or modelling frameworks), pathways and scenario analysis with a poster or roll-up that will be presented in the networking space. **NOTE:** you are invited to bring posters/roll-ups that are not necessarily worked out as research posters but that highlight your models and activities in EU energy transformation research. If you want to present your EU model and discuss about a special EU-scenario/EU-project do not hesitate to ask for two poster places.

Please write a mail with the title(s) of your posters/roll-ups until the **7th of April**.

If you are interested to give an input to a focus group you can directly contact the heads of the groups through to the given contact.

It is possible to register with 2 or 3 persons as long as places are available.

An invitation to contribute to a special volume of the peer reviewed Energy Strategy Reviews will be sent out to all registered persons by the end of March.

¹ Conference of the Parties (COP 23) to the UN Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)
<http://sdg.iisd.org/events/unfccc-cop-23/>

² <http://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regexpert/index.cfm?do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=2981>

³ Recommendation 9.d. Page 14

: <http://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regexpert/index.cfm?do=groupDetail.groupDetailDoc&id=25609&no=1>

Agenda for the EMP-E

DAY 1 May 17	
9:30-10:00	Arrival and set-up
10:00-10:30	Context and goals of EMP-E Berit Müller (RLI) and Patrick van Hove (DG Research)
First Session: commissions view on energy modelling and involved communities	
10:30-11:00	Data openness in EU Energy Models Andreas Zucker (DG JRC)
11:00-11:30	How the European Commission uses energy modelling in policy planning Jan Ole Kiso (DG ENERGY)
11:30-12:00	Fostering European Energy Transformation: Reconciling the modelling and stakeholder communities – (EU-Calc) Jürgen Kropp (PIK)
12:00-13:30	Lunch
Second Session: insights in the LCE 21 projects	
13:30-14:00	Linking models - (SET-Nav) Gustav Resch (TU Wien)
14:00-14:30	Openness, sharing and reproducibility - (MEDEAS) Jordi Sole Ollé (CSIC)
14:30-15:00	Modelling of flexibility and technological progress - (REFLEX) Angelo Martino, (TRT Trasporti e Territorio srl)
15:00-15:30	EU28 decarbonisation pathways: multi-model impact assessment and diagnostics - (REEEM) Mark Howells (KTH)
15:30-16:00	Coffee
Third Session (pathways, sector coupling, case studies)	
16:00-17:45	The ambitious task of setting policy targets for energy efficiency: a multi-scale analysis of societal metabolism - (MAGIC) Maddalena Ripa, Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB)
	Modelling EU cities decarbonisation pathways - (InSMART) Sofia Simoes (NOVA University of Lisbon)
	title not yet defined (ECF) Julien Pestiaux (Climact)
	title not yet defined (SIM4NEXUS) Ioannis Pappis (KTH)
	DAFNE (tbc)
	An adaptable energy systems model (EERA Joint Programme on Energy Systems Integration) Juha Kiviliuoma (VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland)
17:45-18:00	Conclusion and wrap-up
Conference Diner (reservation of location; on the base of self-payment)	

DAY 2 May 18	
8:00-9:15	Arrival, installation of posters and roll-ups
Fourth Session (models and transparency)	
9:15-11:00	Insights from EU Integrated gas and electricity modelling Paul Deane (University College Cork)
	Transparency in EU energy system modelling – METIS open-book approach (METIS) Laurent Fournié (Artelys)
	An adaptable energy systems model (EERA Joint Programme on Energy Systems Integration) Juha Kiviliuoma (VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland)
	title not yet defined - (E3ME) Jean-Francois Mercure (Radboud University Nijmegen) PRIMES Model (E3M lab NTUA) (tbc)
11:00-13:00	Project Networking Space and Lunch
13:00-14:45	Focus Groups - parallel sessions: Designing and comparing energy transition pathways
	Capacity expansion planning in high RES worlds combined with Uncertainty in modelling inputs and outputs
	Structuring of open databases and reproducibility
14:45-15:00	Changing between Focus Groups and Coffee-to-go
15:00-16:45	Focus Groups - parallel sessions: bridging the gap between policy questions and models
	Modelling of environmental impacts and externalities
	Methodologies for linking models
16:45-17:30	Discussion, conclusion and wrap-up

Please confirm your participation and submit the title of your poster/roll-up until **7th of April** at: <http://www.reeem.org/index.php/emp-e/>. The password is 123reeem.

We are looking forward to discuss crucial modelling issues with you at the side of your posters, in the focus groups and in the plenary.

Mark Howells (*KTH*)
Berit Mueller (*RLI*)

on behalf of the REEEM Consortium

Attached you find the deadlines, the contacts for the focus groups and an overview of the scientific committee.

Deadlines

- Registration Deadline and notification of posters/roll-ups 7th of April
- Notification of participation in the after conference diner 7th of April
- Submission of SHORT abstracts for the speeches 23rd April
- **EMP-E conference** 17th/18th May
- Submission of abstracts for a journal paper 26th May
- Invitation to submit a journal paper 7th June
- Submission of journal paper 31st of July

Focus Groups

Designing and comparing energy transition pathways - KTH and IER (contact: gardumi@kth.se (Francesco Gardumi))

Capacity expansion planning in high RES worlds combined with Uncertainty in modelling inputs and outputs - Artelys and KIT (contact: laurent.fournie@artelys.com)

Structuring of open databases and reproducibility - RLI (contact: berit.mueller@rl-institut.de)

Bridging the gap between policy questions and models - TNO (contact: Christian.Bos@tno.nl)

Modelling of environmental impacts and externalities DTU - (contact: keka@dtu.dk (Kenneth Karlsson))

Methodologies for linking models IER and TU Wien (contact: ulrich.fahl@ier.uni-stuttgart.de)

Address of the venue:

21 rue du champ de Mars – marsveldstraat, 1050 Brussels

Scientific committee:

Andreas Zucker	European Commission - Joint Research Centre
Estathios Peteves	European Commission - Joint Research Centre
Jan Ole Kiso	European Commission - Directorate-General for Energy
Patrick van Howe	European Commission - Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
Dogan Keles	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
Luis-Javier Miguel	Universidad de Valladolid
Jordi Sole Olle	Spanish National Research Council - CSIC
Gustav Resch	Technical University Wien
Ulrich Fahl	Institute of Energy Economics and Rational Energy Use, University of Stuttgart
Berit Müller	Reiner Lemoine Institute
Kenneth Karlsson	Technical University of Denmark
Ilkka Keppo	University College London
Mark Howells	Royal Institute of Technology - KTH
Georgios Avgineropoulos	Royal Institute of Technology - KTH
Fancesco Gardumi	Royal Institute of Technology - KTH

Organisation committee:

Berit Müller and Mark Howells for REEEM (RLI, KTH)
Patrick van Howe (European Commission DG RTD)

For any questions contact berit.mueller@rl-institut.de

Welcome to the Energy Modelling Platform for Europe (EMP-E) Start-up meeting 2017, May 17 – 18, EC headquarters, Brussels

Thank you for coming and contributing!

We rate this meeting to be a success if one or more of the following points apply

- You get insights about models and modelling projects you didn't know before
- You gain understanding about the policy messages from different modelling exercises
- You find people to discuss interesting new methods for your research
- You get new ideas for the dissemination of your results
- You think of joining forces with another research group or project which is tackling the same topics as yours
- You want to continue the exchange

Find in this handout

- The agenda of the EMP-E 2017
- A plan of the networking space + a list of the poster titles
- A list of participants

Find on the EMP-E page (<http://www.reeem.org/index.php/event/european-modelling-platform-for-europe-emp-e-2017-in-brussels/>)

- The **abstracts** of the speeches of EMP-E 2017;
- The **call for papers** for the special issue of Energy Strategy Reviews;
- A space for providing a description of your model and its outputs;
- After the meeting: collected presentations of the plenary speeches.

W-LAN is accessible by using the router named EC_Guest. For login, please use login: **Guest_rtd@rtd** and password: **Welcome2RTD**

Any **feedback** about the conference and additional ideas are welcome. You can express it directly to the organisers via mail (berit.mueller@rl-institut.de), twitter using the tag #EMPE17 or on the feedback board in the networking space.

#EMPE17

EMP-E 2017 Agenda

DAY 1 May 17	
9:00-10:00	Arrival and set-up
10:00-10:30	Opening of the EMP-E José Cotta, Head of unit "Advanced Energy Production", DG Research & Innovation (EC)
	Context and goals of EMP-E Berit Müller (RLI) and Patrick Van Hove (DG Research & Innovation - EC)
First Session: Energy modelling practice at European level and involved communities	
10:30-10:35	Introduction by the moderator (Mark Howells, KTH)
10:35-10:55	How the European Commission uses energy modelling in policy planning Tom Howes (DG Energy - EC)
10:55-11:15	Data openness in EU Energy Models Andreas Zucker (DG JRC - EC)
11:15-11:35	Market equilibrium models of energy and the economy and their use supporting European Commission's impact assessments Pantelis Capros (E3Modelling Lab, National Technical University of Athens)
11:35-12:05	Fostering European Energy Transformation: Reconciling the modelling and stakeholder communities – (EU-Calc) Jürgen Kropp (PIK)
12:05-13:20	Lunch
Second Session: insights in the LCE 21 projects	
13:20-13:30	Introduction by the moderator Patrick Van Hove (DG Research & Innovation - EC)
13:30-14:00	Linking models - SET-Nav Gustav Resch (TU Wien)
14:00-14:30	Openness, sharing and reproducibility - MEDEAS Jordi Sole Olle (CSIC)
14:30-15:00	Modelling of flexibility and technological progress - Reflex Angelo Martino (TRT Trasporti e Territorio srl)
15:00-15:30	EU28 decarbonisation pathways: multi-model impact assessment and diagnostics - REEEM Mark Howells (KTH)
15:30-16:00	Coffee
Third Session: Pathways, sector coupling, case studies	
16:00 -16:05	Introduction by the moderator Joan Canton (DG Energy - EC)
16:05-17:20	The ambitious task of setting policy targets for energy efficiency: a multi-scale analysis of societal metabolism - MAGIC Maddalena Ripa, Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB)
	Modelling EU cities decarbonisation pathways - InSMART Sofia Simoes (NOVA University of Lisbon)
	ECF's Energy Union Choices report : integrated gas/electricity/demand infrastructure modelling - ECF Laurent Noirhomme (Climact)
	Insights from EU Integrated gas and electricity modelling Paul Deane (University College Cork)
17:20-18:00	Energy modelling and the Nexus concept: design and tools in SIM4NEXUS - SIM4NEXUS Floor Brouwer (Wageningen Economic Research); Hector Pollitt (Cambridge Econometrics)
	Discussion on continuation EMP-E
19:00	Conference Dinner (on the base of self-payment and reservation) at Kafenio, Rue Stevin 134

DAY 2 May 18	
8:00 - 9:00	Arrival, installation of posters
	Fourth Session: Models and transparency
9:00 - 9:05	Introduction by the Moderator (Berit Müller, RLI)
9:05 - 9:25	Models in Energy System Analyses Michael Grubb (University College London)
9:25-10:45	Transparency in EU energy system modelling – METIS open-book approach (METIS) Tobias Bossmann (Artelys)
	POTEnCIA: An innovative, technology-rich, policy-oriented, open model to address EU energy scenarios Tobias Wiesenthal (DG JRC)
	An adaptable energy systems model (EERA Joint Programme on Energy Systems Integration) Juha Kiviliuoma (VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland)
	Modelling complex systems of heterogeneous agents to better design sustainability transitions policy - (E3ME) Jean-Francois Mercure (Radboud University Nijmegen)
	The PRIMES Model Alessia de Vita (E3M lab NTUA)
10:45-11:30	Preview on networking space (1min/poster)
11:30-13:30	Project Networking Space and Lunch
13:30-15:15	Focus Groups - parallel sessions:
	Designing and comparing energy transition pathways
	Capacity expansion planning in high RES worlds combined with Uncertainty in modelling inputs and outputs
	Publishing in open databases and increase of transparency and reproducibility
15:15-15:30	Changing between Focus Groups and Coffee-to-go
15:30-17:15	Focus Groups - parallel sessions:
	Bridging the gap between policy questions and models
	Modelling of environmental impacts and externalities
17:15-17:30	Methodologies for linking models
17:15-17:30	Conclusion and wrap-up

Plan of the networking space

DD = Different Dimensions of Energy Modelling

F = Flexibility/Storage

M = Models

MM = Model Matrix

T = towards more transparency in European energy system analyses

E = environmental impacts of the energy sector

P = Pathways

S = modelling at different scales

List of Posters

Different Dimensions of Energy Modelling		
DD.1	Ruud Egging (NTNU)	SET-Nav - case studies on Europe's strategic energy technologies
DD.2	Gustav Resch (TU Wien)	SET-Nav - the project at a glance
DD.3	Angelo Martino (TRT)	Reflex - Analysis of the European Energy System under the Aspects of Flexibility and Technological Progress
DD.4	Linas Martišauskas (LEI)	Methodology for energy security assessment considering energy system resistance to disruptions
DD.5	Arash Shojachaikar (ZIRIUS)	Linking social science and energy modeling: Inclusion of social system analysis in modeling practices
DD.6	Behnam Zakeri	Interconnection of the UK to the Nordic power market -- Impacts on social welfare and renewable integration
Flexibility/Storage		
F.1	Arjuna Nebel (WI)	Modeling the interdependencies of storage, dsm and grid extension for europe
F.2	Frank Meinke-Hubeny	ESTMAP – Energy Storage Mapping and Planning, Energy System analysis (2 roll-ups)
Models		
M.1	Ndaona Chokani	EnerPol: High-Resolution Integrated Framework for Analysis of Electricity, Gas, Transport and Urban Systems
M.2	Jody Dillon (UCD)	Epiphron - A flexible tool for modelling high VG systems across multiple time scales
M.3	Jonas Hörsch (FIAS)	PyPSA-EU-Grid: An Open Optimization Model of the European Transmission System
M.4	Valentin Bertsch, Muireann Lynch, Mel Devine (ESRI)	Models for Quantifying Benefits of Integrated Energy Systems
M.5	Vidas Lekavicius (LEI)	Linking CGE and Energy Planning Models – a Case Study for Lithuania
M.6	Pinar Korkomaz (IER)	Model based analysis of transformation pathways to a sustainable European energy system
M.7	Alexis Laurent and Serena Fabbri (DTU)	Assessing environmental impacts of future energy systems: a holistic LCA model for Europe in 2015-2050
M.8	Wided Medroubi (Next Energy)	SciGRID: a first experience with creating and publishing open data and models of the European power transmission network
M.9	Berit Müller (RLI)	open energy modelling framework (oemof)
M.10	Roland Montenegro (IER)	Multi-sectoral modelling of decarbonisation pathways: a pilot thought experiment
MM		Model-Matrix

Towards more transparency in European energy system analyses		
T.1	Ludwig Hülk (RLI)	The OpenEnergy Database (oedb) - A database concept to improve transparency in energy system analyses
T.2	Georgios Avgerinopoulos (KTH)	Energydata.info - An innovation of the World Bank
T.3	Robbie Morrison (openmod)	Improving energy sysetem modelling: the Open Energy Modelling Initiative
T.4	Pierre Iachetti (EURAC)	Hotmaps. Heating and Cooling: Open Source Tool for Mapping and Planning of Energy Systems
Environmental impacts of the energy sector		
E.1	Ulla Mörtberg (KTH)	The Landscape simulation and Ecological Assessment (LECA) tool - A case study of Lithuania
E.2	Dorothea Schmid (IER)	Analysis of impacts of different emission reduction scenarios on emission unit prices in Europe
Pathways		
P.2	Laura Gutierrez (IRENA)	IRENA's work for a Global Renewable Energy Future: 1) Key programmes and activities; 2) REmap (Renewable Energy Roadmap)
P.3	Christian Bussar (RWTH Aachen)	GENESYS 2: Optimisation of Pathways Towards a Low-Carbon European Energy System
P.4	Antoine Levesque (PIK)	Improving REMIND to create more detailed EU decarbonization scenarios for the INNOPATHS project
P.5	Heidi Ursula Heinrichs (FZJ)	Towards transparency - the issue of socio-economic scenario frameworks
Modelling at different scales		
S.1	Sofia Simoes (UNL)	Integrative Smart City Planning – Urban energy system modelling
S.2	Pia Manz (ISI)	Modelling electricity demand with high spatial and temporal resolution

List of participants

Alessia	de Vita	E3MLab
Alexis	Laurent	DTU - Technical University of Denmark
Andreas	Zucker	EC - Joint Research Centre
Angelo	Martino	TRT Trasporti e Territorio
Anna	Darmani	InnoEnergy
Antoine	Levesque	PIK Potsdam
Antoine	MONNET	LGI
Arash	Shojachaikar	University of Stuttgart, ZIRIUS
Arjuna	Nebel	Wuppertalinstitut
Arvydas	Galinis	Lithuanian Energy Institute
Behnam	Zakeri	Aalto University
Berit	Müller	Reiner Lemoine Institut
Bert	Saveyn	EC - Joint Research Centre (JRC)
Christian	Bos	TNO
Christian	Bussar	RWTH Aachen
Christiane	DE RACHE	EC - DG Research and Innovation
Claude	Ayache	InnoEnergy
Claudia	Zabel	IER, University of Stuttgart
Christopher	Andrey	Artelys
Dogan	Keles	KIT; Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
Dorothea	Schmid	IER, University of Stuttgart
Dries	Acke	European Climate foundation
Esthios	Peteves	EC - Joint Research Centre (JRC)
Francesco	Gardumi	Royal Institute of Technology - KTH
Frank	Meinke-Hubeny	EnergyVille
Fiac	Gaffney	University College Cork
Florinus	Brouwer	Wageningen Economic Research
Georgios	Avgerinopoulos	Royal Institute of Technology - KTH
Gustav	Resch	Technical University Wien
Hector	Pollitt	Cambridge Econometrics
Heidi Ursula	Heinrichs	FZJ (research center Jülich)
Herib	Blanco	University of Groningen
Ilkka	Keppo	UCL - University College London
Ioannis	Pappis	Royal Institute of Technology - KTH
Jan Ole	Kiso	UK Government - EU-ETS Team
Jasper Lux	Geipel	Technical University Wien
Jean-François	Mercure	Radboud University Nijmegen
Jody	Dillon	University College Dublin
Jonas	Hörsch	Frankfurt Institute for Advanced Studies (FIAS)
Jordi	Sole Olle	Spanish National Research Council - CSIC
Jose	Cotta	EC - DG Research and Innovation
Juha	Kiviluoma	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland
Julien	Pestiaux	Climact
Jürgen	Kropp	Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research — PIK
Kaddy Sabally	Müller	Reiner Lemoine Institut
Kenneth	Karlson	DTU - Technical University of Denmark
Laszlo	Szabo	REKK - Regional Centre for Energy Policy Research

Laura Isabel	Gutiérrez Medina	IRENA
Laurent	Noirhomme	Climact
Lei	Xu	KIT; Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
Leonie	Beekman	TNO
Linas	Martišauskas	Lithuanian Energy Institute
Ludwig	Hülk	Reiner Lemoine Institut
Maddalena	Ripa	Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB)
Mariana	Stantcheva	EC - Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (INEA)
Mark	Howells	Royal Institute of Technology - KTH
Mark	O'Malley	University College Dublin
Matthias	Kuehnbach	Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research
Mel	Devine	Economic and Social Research Institute
Michael	Grubb	University College London
Mirjam	Groote Schaarsberg	TNO
Muireann	Lynch	Economic and Social Research Institute
Ndaona	Chokani	ETH Zürich
Olavur	Ellefsen	TOKNI
Oliver	Sartor	IDDR
Pantelis	Capros	E3MLab
Patrick	Van Hove	EC - DG Research and Innovation
Paul	Deane	University College Cork
Peter	HORVATH	EC - DG Research and Innovation
Pia	Manz	Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research
Pierre Deane	Iachetti	EURAC
Pinar	Korkmaz	IER, University of Stuttgart
Rainer	Friedrich	IER, University of Stuttgart
Robbie	Morrison	openmod
Roland	Cunha Montenegro	IER, University of Stuttgart
Rudolf	Gerardus Egging	NTNU - Norwegian University of Science and Technology
Serena	Fabbri	DTU - Technical University of Denmark
Sofia	Simoës	NOVA University of Lisbon
Steve	Pye	UCL - University College London
Tobias	BOSSMANN	Artelys
Tobias	Wiesenthal	EC - JRC
Tom	Howes	EC - DG Energy
Toon	Vandyck	EC - Joint Research Centre (JRC)
Ulla	Mörtberg	Royal Institute of Technology - KTH
Ulrich	Fahl	IER, University of Stuttgart
Valentin	Bertsch	Economic and Social Research Institute
Vidas	Lekavičius	Lithuanian Energy Institute
Vincent	Matton	Climact
Wided	Medjroubi	NEXT ENERGY

Special Issue of Energy Strategy Reviews (Elsevier): *Energy transition and decarbonisation pathways for the EU*

Preface

This open access Special Issue is a peer-reviewed collection of results from the first meeting of the Energy Modelling Platform for Europe (EMP-E), held on May 17th and 18th at the premises of European Commission's DG Research. It brings together contributions by the EC-funded projects and European energy modelling groups participating in the event.

The Special Issue constitutes a peer-reviewed digest of models, approaches and policy insights for the assessment of energy transition and decarbonisation pathways in the European Union, vis-à-vis the Energy Union and the Strategic Energy Technology (SET) Plan. It provides academics and decision makers with a deep review of cutting-edge EU-focused energy modelling research.

The Special Issue is structured in two sub-sections:

- modelling tools and methodologies;
- case studies and policy insights.

The first section collects conceptual papers presenting models and methodologies for the assessment of energy transition pathways. Contributions include reviews of the models, their characteristics, the range of analyses they allow and an indication of their strengths and limitations. Methodologies for cross-sectoral impact analyses through soft- or hard-linking of the models are also covered. Finally, original work on the approaches to scenario definition and analysis are collected.

The second section presents case studies highlighting policy insights and key messages which can be obtained with the different tools. The case studies are to have an EU focus with regional, national and sub-national representation and implications (or vice versa). This part of the Special Issue illuminates dynamics that EU and member state policy makers should have access to, to potentially inform engagements in the Conference of the Parties (COP23) as well as other milestone meetings.

Call for contributions

We hereby open the call for contributions to the Special Issue ***Energy transition and decarbonisation pathways for the EU***. We invite you to submit full papers and we ask your kind availability to review other contributions, in order to ensure for all submissions a fast process through to the publication.

In line with the structure and concept of the Special Issue, papers are highly welcome in one of the following formats:

- Methodology article (up to 10-12 pages, but also shorter), describing your model and methodology;
- Case study (up to 4 pp, with supplementary material uploaded online), representing a relevant application and the insights obtained from it.

However, contributions are welcome also in the format of:

- Short review/Report review (1-5 pp);

- Analysis (up to 10-12 pp);
- Viewpoint/Energy visions (2-4 pp).

A description of the types of articles and instructions for the preparation of the manuscripts are available at:

https://www.elsevier.com/wps/find/journaldescription.cws_home/725839?generatepdf=true

Instructions on the submission process will come shortly.

The deadline for the submission of full papers is July 15th.